

IMPROVING THE QUALITY OF TEACHING IN ENGLISH ON THE BASIS OF PROVERBS AND SAYINGS

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Annotation. In this article, the author studies the role of proverbs and sayings in improving the quality of teaching English. In the course of teaching English on the basis of proverbs and sayings, students develop their communicative competence.

Key words: English language, proverbs and sayings, competence, communicativeness.

The purpose of teaching foreign languages does not differ only in the formation of language skills and speech skills. The competent approach expands the practical component of the learning goal: in the course of teaching English on the basis of proverbs and sayings, students develop their communicative competence through which the emerging formation of the remaining key and (at the profile stage of education) the simplest foundations of professional competencies in order to solve the problems of social activity in its various areas.

Significantly important components of communicative competence are:

“linguistic (knowledge of grammar and vocabulary), discursive (the study of the language used by members of a certain language community. In the course of such an analysis, both the form of the language and its function are considered.), pragmatic (a set of conditions that accompany the use of a linguistic sign), strategic (non-detailed a plan covering a long period of time, a way to achieve a complex goal) and a socio-cultural (methodological approach based on a systematic approach)”

Lexical competence is an integral part of the communicative one, the

formation of which proceeds as a graduated process; several levels can be conditionally distinguished in it. Under the level of formation of lexical competence, we mean the ability of students to solve problems related to the assimilation of a foreign word in the practical use of it in speech on the basis of acquired knowledge and relevant skills.

The structure of lexical competence includes: cognitive component, operational-activity, effective-practical, socio-cultural and reflective components.

The cognitive component is offered by lexical knowledge. Under lexical knowledge, knowledge of clear lexical units, knowledge of the meaning of a certain lexical-semantic variant, knowledge of the form of a word (phonetic, graphic, grammatical, morphological, word-building, lexical, semantic, syntactic series of the language) is considered.

An operational-activity component, which, in principle, is ready to describe the communicative content in a communication situation. It includes the skills and abilities to express statements in accordance with the lexical norms of the language being studied.

The effective-practical or procedural component involves a strategy for mastering the word, which includes certain actions on the word. These are linguodidactic strategies. Linguodidactic strategies reflect the model of a secondary linguistic personality, the model of mastering the system of a non-native language and culture.

These strategies - semantic, linguosystematizing, cognitive-conceptual (linguocultural) provide a constant search for meanings in a wide socio-cultural context, the selection and accumulation of linguistic means, the expansion of the language base, the generalization of the language being studied into an ordered, personally significant system, its constant replenishment and updating using one's own language and speech experience, including in the native language, mastering the corresponding system of concepts, concepts, penetration into the culture of a native speaker, understanding national and cultural specifics at the level of

intercultural communication.

The sociocultural component of lexical competence implies knowledge of the cultural diversity of vocabulary, possession of lexical samples of the official and unofficial style.

The reflexive component involves specific practical strategies, which, in conditions of independent language learning, include mastering language tools, independent training and speech practice, content in various situations of verbal communication and the use of the language being studied as a means of performing various functional tasks. The reflexive component is associated with self-control, by which we mean the quality of the personality associated with the manifestation of its activity and independence.

As part of our study, it was determined that proverbs and sayings are the subject of study of a special science - paremiology, which, along with them, explores almost all set expressions in the language - phraseological units, wellerisms, slogans, aphorisms, maxims, riddles, signs, etc. The main difference between proverbs and sayings here is the lack of authorship. This means that their origin is not traceable to any literary author's text or statement. Otherwise, proverbs and sayings are similar to other proverbs, or paremiological clichés.

The very fact of the existence of such invariant meanings common to many proverbs allows us to make the following assumption. Proverbs and sayings as genres of oral folk art are a means of conceptualizing reality, i.e. in a certain sense, in its purpose, it approaches the lexeme and contributes to the performance of such language functions as cognitive, imperative, aesthetic. To the least extent, proverbs and sayings contribute to the implementation of the communicative function of the language.

In our opinion, this issue is in the field of view of linguoculturology.

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